

On the generalized constructive set

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Abstract In this paper, we use the elementary methods to study the properties of the constructive set S , and obtain some interesting properties for it.

Keywords Generalized constructive set, summation, recurrence equation, characteristic equation.

§1. Introduction and Results

The generalized constructive set S is defined as: numbers formed by digits d_1, d_2, \dots, d_m only, all d_i being different each other, $1 \leq m \leq 9$. That is to say,

- (1) d_1, d_2, \dots, d_m belongs to S ;
- (2) If a, b belong to S , then \overline{ab} belongs to S too;
- (3) Only elements obtained by rules (1) and (2) applied a finite number of times belongs to S .

For example, the constructive set (of digits 1, 2) is: 1, 2, 11, 12, 21, 22, 111, 112, 121, 122, 211, 212, 221, 222, 1111, 1112, 1121, \dots . And the constructive set (of digits 1, 2, 3) is: 1, 2, 3, 11, 12, 13, 21, 22, 23, 31, 32, 33, 111, 112, 113, 121, 122, 123, 131, 132, 133, 211, 212, 213, 221, 222, 223, 231, 232, 233, 311, 312, 313, 321, 322, 323, 331, 332, 333, 1111, \dots . In problem 6, 7 and 8 of reference [1], Professor F.Smarandache asked us to study the properties of this sequence. In [2], Gou Su had studied the convergent properties of the series

$$\sum_{n=1}^{+\infty} \frac{1}{a_n^\alpha},$$

and proved that the series is convergent if $\alpha > \log m$, and divergent if $\alpha \leq \log m$, where $\{a_n\}$ denotes the sequence of the constructive set S , formed by digits d_1, d_2, \dots, d_m only, all d_i being different each other, $1 \leq m \leq 9$.

In this paper, we shall use the elementary methods to study the summation $\sum_{k=1}^n S_k$ and $\sum_{k=1}^n T_k$, where S_k denotes the summation of all k digits numbers in S , T_k denotes the summation of each digits of all k digits numbers in S .

That is, we shall prove the following

Theorem 1. For the generalized constructive set S of digits d_1, d_2, \dots, d_m ($1 \leq m \leq 9$), we have

$$\sum_{k=1}^n S_k = \frac{d_1 + d_2 + \dots + d_m}{9} \left(10 \times \frac{(10m)^n - 1}{10m - 1} - \frac{m^n - 1}{m - 1} \right),$$

where S_k denotes the summation of all k digits numbers in S .

Taking $m = 2$, $d_1 = 1$ and $d_2 = 2$ in Theorem 1, we may immediately get

Corollary 1. For the generalized constructive set S of digits 1 and 2, we have

$$\sum_{k=1}^n S_k = \frac{1}{3} \left(10 \times \frac{20^n - 1}{19} - 2^n + 1 \right).$$

Taking $m = 3$, $d_1 = 1$, $d_2 = 2$ and $d_3 = 3$ in Theorem 1, we may immediately get the following:

Corollary 2. For the generalized constructive set S of digits 1, 2 and 3, we have

$$\sum_{k=1}^n S_k = \frac{2}{3} \left(10 \times \frac{30^n - 1}{29} - \frac{3^n}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \right).$$

Theorem 2. For the generalized constructive set S of digits d_1, d_2, \dots, d_m ($1 \leq m \leq 9$), we have

$$\sum_{k=1}^n T_k = (d_1 + d_2 + \dots + d_m) \cdot \frac{nm^{n+1} - (n+1)m^n + 1}{(m-1)^2},$$

where T_k denotes the summation of each digits of all k digits numbers in S .

Taking $m = 2$, $d_1 = 1$ and $d_2 = 2$ in Theorem 2, we may immediately get the following:

Corollary 3. For the the generalized constructive set S of digits 1 and 2, we have

$$\sum_{k=1}^n T_k = 3n \cdot 2^{n+1} - 3(n+1)2^n + 3.$$

Taking $m = 3$, $d_1 = 1$, $d_2 = 2$ and $d_3 = 3$ in Theorem 2, we may immediately get

Corollary 4. For the the generalized constructive set S of digits 1, 2 and 3, we have

$$\sum_{k=1}^n T_k = \frac{3}{2}n \cdot 3^{n+1} - \frac{3}{2}(n+1)3^n + \frac{3}{2}.$$

§2. Proof of the theorems

In this section, we shall complete the proof of the theorems. First we prove Theorem 1. Let S_k denotes the summation of all k digits numbers in the generalized constructive set S . Note that for $k = 1, 2, 3, \dots$, there are m^k numbers of k digits in S . So we have

$$S_k = 10^{k-1}m^{k-1}(d_1 + d_2 + \dots + d_m) + mS_{k-1}. \quad (1)$$

Meanwhile, we have

$$S_{k-1} = 10^{k-2}m^{k-2}(d_1 + d_2 + \dots + d_m) + mS_{k-2}. \quad (2)$$

Combining (1) and (2), we can get the following recurrence equation

$$S_k - 11mS_{k-1} + 10m^2S_{k-2} = 0.$$

Its characteristic equation

$$x^2 - 11mx + 10m^2 = 0$$

have two different real solutions

$$x = m, 10m.$$

So we let

$$S_k = A \cdot m^k + B \cdot (10m)^k.$$

Note that

$$S_0 = 0, \quad S_1 = d_1 + d_2 + \cdots + d_m,$$

we can get

$$A = -\frac{d_1 + d_2 + \cdots + d_m}{9m}, \quad B = \frac{d_1 + d_2 + \cdots + d_m}{9m}.$$

So

$$S_k = \frac{d_1 + d_2 + \cdots + d_m}{9m} ((10m)^k - m^k).$$

Then

$$\sum_{k=1}^n S_k = \frac{d_1 + d_2 + \cdots + d_m}{9} \left(10 \times \frac{(10m)^n - 1}{10m - 1} - \frac{m^n - 1}{m - 1} \right).$$

This completes the proof of Theorem 1.

Now we come to prove Theorem 2. Let T_k is denotes the summation of each digits of all k digits numbers in the generalized constructive set S .

Similarly, note that for $k = 1, 2, 3, \dots$, there are m^k numbers of k digits in S , so we have

$$T_k = m^{k-1}(d_1 + d_2 + \cdots + d_m) + mT_{k-1} \quad (3)$$

Meanwhile, we have

$$T_{k-1} = m^{k-2}(d_1 + d_2 + \cdots + d_m) + mT_{k-2} \quad (4)$$

Combining (3) and (4), we can get the following recurrence equation

$$T_k - 2mT_{k-1} + m^2T_{k-2} = 0,$$

its characteristic equation

$$x^2 - 2mx + m^2 = 0$$

have two solutions

$$x_1 = x_2 = m.$$

So we let

$$T_k = A \cdot m^k + k \cdot B \cdot m^k.$$

Note that

$$T_0 = 0, \quad T_1 = d_1 + d_2 + \cdots + d_m.$$

We may immediately deduce that

$$A = 0, \quad B = \frac{d_1 + d_2 + \cdots + d_m}{m}.$$

So

$$T_k = (d_1 + d_2 + \cdots + d_m) \cdot km^{k-1}.$$

Then

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{k=1}^n T_k &= (d_1 + d_2 + \cdots + d_m) \sum_{k=1}^n k \cdot m^{k-1} \\ &= (d_1 + d_2 + \cdots + d_m) \left(\sum_{k=1}^n m^k \right)' \\ &= (d_1 + d_2 + \cdots + d_m) \cdot \frac{nm^{n+1} - (n+1)m^n + 1}{(m-1)^2}. \end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof of Theorem 2.

References

- [1] F. Smarandache, Only Problems, Not Solutions, Chicago, Xiquan Publishing House, 1993.
- [2] Gou Su, On the generalized constructive set, Research on Smarandache problems in number theory, Hexis, 2005, 53-55.